

A UNIVERSAL TOOL FOR GENERATING DATASETS FROM SOUND SYNTHESIZERS

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces an open-source software tool designed to simplify the process of generating datasets from sound synthesizers and other sound-generating devices. These devices can be either hardware or software, as well as electronic or acoustic, provided they can be interfaced using standard protocols commonly found in sound synthesizers. The tool supports four paradigms for changing synthesis parameters and musical notes within the dataset generation process, enabling comprehensive control of sound generation while ensuring precise audio recording with accurate timing. Dataset generation is fully automated, significantly reducing the need for manual intervention and making the process efficient, reliable, and reproducible. The tool's extensive features are accessible through a graphical user interface. The dataset is organized as a collection of audio files, while notes and parameter information are stored in a tabular format, facilitating further use through offline scripts. This paper details the design and functionality of the tool and discusses its alignment with a previous release focused on audio effects dataset generation, thereby providing a comprehensive suite of resources for generating datasets from musical devices.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Sound Synthesizers

Sound synthesizers are electronic devices that generate audio signals using analog or digital processing techniques. Widely used in music production and performances, these devices allow detailed control over musical elements such as frequency, amplitude, timbre, and the timing of sonic events (i.e., the notes). They transform musical scores into audible signals, distinguishing themselves from other sound generators used in sonic interaction design, where such control is typically unnecessary [1].

Until the 1960s, analog sound synthesizers were large, expensive, and mainly found in labs rather than studios or stages, requiring complex patching of oscillators and filters to create sounds. In the 1970s, they became smaller, commercially available and widespread across various music genres. By the 1980s, microprocessors enabled precise parameter control and preset storage, paving the way for

fully digital sound synthesizers. These instruments often integrated keyboards and expressive controls, though many were available solely as modular units with electrical-only input/output (I/O). By the mid-1990s, digital synthesizers emerged as software-based devices for use in digital audio workstations on personal computers.

Over the last 50 years, various sound synthesis techniques have emerged, including additive, subtractive, frequency modulation, sample-based, wavetable, vector, granular, concatenative, and neural synthesis, and combinations thereof [2]. These methods can produce a wide range of timbres, mimicking acoustic instruments and creating novel sounds. Techniques like physical modeling and virtual analog have also been developed to emulate the sound-generating mechanisms of acoustic and analog synthesizers [3, 4]. Instead of replacing older methods, new advancements enrich the ecosystem for musicians and sound artists, broadening creative possibilities in sound design.

1.1.1 Synthesizers Inputs and Outputs

From an I/O perspective, a sound synthesizer translates symbolic-music information into sound, bridging two significantly different domains. In addition to musical information, the input may also include static or dynamic synthesis parameters that are used to shape their timbre. The input and output of the sound synthesis core are analog or digital electrical signals, even when an arbitrary musical interface is integrated into the device.

Most sound synthesizers offer mono or stereo audio output, though some 3D audio synthesizers provide more channels. Hardware devices use standard connectors like RCA, TRS, or XLR for analog signals. Digital outputs like S/PDIF or audio-over-USB are increasingly popular, especially in digital synthesizers. Eurorack format synthesizers, common in modular systems, typically output at 10 V_{PP} on a 3.5 mm TS jack, requiring attenuation for compatibility with line-level voltages.

Symbolic musical information is usually transmitted to hardware synthesizers via MIDI, using multipolar cables with five-pin DIN or USB connectors. MIDI is also common in analog synthesizers, allowing polyphonic and multi-parametric control through a single cable. Notes are triggered by 'Note On' messages with pitch and velocity, and ended with 'Note Off' messages. Modular synthesizers use two analog signals for note triggering: a pitch-controlling signal, often Volts per Octave (V/Oct), and a 'Gate' pulse, which may influence the amplitude and sustain. The lack of standards in modular systems leads to variation in Gate signal voltage levels and their use in con-

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trolling the sustain phase, if utilized at all. Furthermore, achieving polyphony requires multiple I/Os and cables, resulting in a setup that is significantly more complex than MIDI interfacing.

Hardware synthesizers typically feature knobs, sliders, switches, and buttons for adjusting synthesis parameters. In analog synthesizers, these controls directly impact electrical components, whereas in digital synthesizers, they modify variables within synthesis algorithms, often represented on user-friendly displays. MIDI can also adjust parameters using ‘Continuous Controller’ (CC) messages, though MIDI 1.0’s 7-bit resolution is limiting compared to the higher resolution of onboard controls or modern DSP needs. MIDI 2.0, offering up to 32-bit resolution, is yet limited in availability. Modular synthesizers use DC-coupled Control Voltage (CV) signals for parameter control, which can range from -10 to 10 V and provide theoretically infinite resolution, but each parameter needs its own wire. Digital modules sample CVs with 10- to 16-bit converters, offering less resolution than expected.

Most software synthesizers function as plugins in Virtual Studio Technology (VST) or Audio Units (AU) formats, integrating seamlessly with Digital Audio Workstations (DAWs). Audio output uses channel-interleaved buffers with sample sizes determined by the host or drivers, using 32- or 64-bit floating-point numbers. Signal levels usually range from -1 to 1 , though some plugins allow higher levels, requiring careful management to prevent clipping. VST and AU plugins support MIDI for note information, using 7-bit resolution for the chromatic scale from $A0$ to $C8$. Synthesis parameters are represented as 32- or 64-bit floating-point numbers, normalized between 0 and 1.

Acoustic and electroacoustic instruments can be treated like sound synthesizers and utilized with the proposed tool for generating datasets, provided they are equipped with hardware that enables electrical I/O. The output process is straightforward: the sound of acoustic instruments can be captured using microphones, while electroacoustic instruments typically feature magnetic or piezoelectric pickups that generate analog signals. The input side is more complex, as it requires the installation of specialized electromechanical actuators to replicate the actions of human players. Various acoustic and electroacoustic instruments have been modified for this purpose, known as robotic musical instruments [5, 6]. These instruments usually provide control through standard protocols such as MIDI.

1.2 Structures of Sound Synthesizer Datasets

A dataset collected from a sound synthesizer generally includes audio recordings of its output, accompanied by inputs like notes and synthesis parameters. The choice of inputs is generally application-specific: recordings may focus on individual notes with variations like duration and dynamics, chords, or entire melodies. Recordings might capture the full note or specific phases, such as the attack or release. Synthesis parameters can be varied to capture different timbres produced by a specific technique. Synthesizers often have extensive parameter sets, making it crucial to select which to vary to avoid excessive dataset

size. Typically, recordings are made with fixed parameter combinations, though sometimes parameters are dynamically varied during recording.

There is no standard method for organizing dataset files and information. However, efforts are being made to reduce variability in experimental outcomes by developing open-source libraries that manage datasets in their existing formats [7]. Sound synthesizer datasets often feature a separate uncompressed audio file for each input combination, with input details and metadata linked through CSV files or tabular formats. Less commonly, input details are encoded in file names. Audio sample rates within a dataset are usually consistent, though they vary across datasets, with common rates being 44.1, 48, and 96 kHz. Some datasets use a single audio recording, with time tags for segmentation according to inputs. Scripts for loading datasets into scientific computing environments or datasets in ready-to-import binary formats may also be provided. Datasets intended for machine learning often include instructions for dividing them into training and testing sets to ensure uniform task evaluation.

1.3 Uses of Datasets for Sound Synthesizer Research

In most fields, data is an essential asset that enables the execution of research work, and this holds true for a wide range of studies related to sound synthesizers or acoustic musical instruments. Datasets from sound synthesizers can be highly valuable in research focused on modeling sound synthesis, particularly in virtual analog synthesis [8–10]. These modeling approaches can also be extended to acoustic musical instruments, with datasets collected from electromechanically-actuated instruments [11]. Datasets of sound synthesizers, including digital ones, also play a key role in the large body of work falling under the umbrella of neural audio synthesis [12]. This ranges from neural networks creating systems that can function similarly to musical instruments to independent and autonomous generative systems.

Datasets can also be utilized to analyze the relationship between synthesis parameters and the generated sound, particularly from a perceptual perspective. Such knowledge is highly valuable in the context of musical human-computer interaction, especially in interfaces for musical expression. By introducing ‘perceptual layers’ [13], which leverage on such knowledge, in the mapping between a performer’s gestures and synthesis parameters can become more expressive. This approach has influenced a range of works in the field, including studies on mapping techniques that utilize machine learning [14–16]. In a similar vein, understanding the perceptual relationship between parameters and sound is crucial when training co-creative intelligent agents designed to learn how to control sound synthesizers by machine-listening [17]. Additionally, datasets are crucial for research into techniques for automatic synthesis programming, particularly in identifying parameters that match a target sound [18, 19]. Datasets are crucial for developing neural synthesis approaches that offer latent spaces to interactively navigate and manipulate timbre. These techniques use perceptually relevant sound rep-

representations, often with visualizations, to improve user understanding and interaction [20, 21].

Datasets from sound synthesizers are vital for music information retrieval tasks like automatic transcription, instrument recognition, classification, and separation [22, 23]. In audio engineering, they aid in characterizing, measuring, and analyzing synthesizer sounds across different batches, techniques, implementations, manufacturers, or after various operating conditions. These datasets also preserve and share over a century of pioneering and commercial sound synthesis work. With nearly 2,400 standalone hardware synthesizer models introduced [24], datasets can document unique sounds and provide a legacy resource for future researchers and musicians. Creatively, these datasets offer a rich sonic corpus, that can be utilized with granular or concatenative synthesis systems [25], and serve as resources for music production or other artistic works.

1.4 Challenges in Creating Synthesizer Datasets

When these datasets are not yet available as secondary data, they must be generated or collected. The associated literature often documents the significant efforts of scholars in assembling the datasets needed for their sound synthesis-related research. Generating such datasets can be tedious and time-consuming. For example, creating a dataset that includes just 3 different notes at 3 different velocities, and 4 synthesis parameters with just 10 sampled values each, requires generating 90,000 unique combinations of note information and parameters. If we record just 2 seconds of audio for each case, this translates to 50 hours of continuous recording time. Moreover, if this process is carried out manually, changing the synthesis inputs can be error-prone and inaccurate. Consistency in interfacing settings, levels, timing, and synchronization of inputs and outputs is critical, especially when sample-level accuracy is desired. Inaccurate datasets can be detrimental to specific applications utilizing them, causing the outcomes to lack precision or contain flaws that are eventually traced back to the data. An alternative approach is to develop ad-hoc automated systems for dataset collection, though this also requires considerable time, expertise, and effort to implement and validate such systems. Furthermore, due to the diverse range of inputs and outputs interfacing across different synthesizers, as described in Section 1.1.1, the development of an automated system may exhibit limited reusability in other contexts.

The challenges described vary based on the dataset's nature. For datasets focused on existing musical phrases with minimal parameter changes and organized into a few recordings, a DAW can simplify the process. However, for systematic sampling of synthesizer responses with varied input patterns and an emphasis on parameter variation, the challenges remain significant.

When datasets are collected using software synthesis algorithms with accessible or easily re-implementable source code, automated and offline audio rendering is a common practice. However, software sound synthesizers implemented as VST plugins have also been used in research, providing more realistic and complex case studies.

RenderMan [26] is a command-line VST instrument host with Python bindings, written in C++. It offers an efficient solution for developing scripts to collect data from VST synthesizers and also includes facilities for analyzing the rendered audio, similar to one of our previously proposed tools [15]. RenderMan is no longer maintained, and its key features have been integrated into DawDreamer [27], which is an audio-processing Python framework that supports core DAW features and more. While both RenderMan and DawDreamer provide some degree of generality in supporting software synthesizers and have been used to develop custom Python scripts for collecting data from specific VST synthesizers, they are fundamentally frameworks without GUI. They do not offer a ready-made solution for automating and organizing the dataset generation process, which must be coded and developed from scratch. Although scripts can be created, interaction with the GUI of the VST for identifying key information essential to defining what should be included in the dataset is limited. Furthermore, DawDreamer, by its design, does not support interfacing with hardware synthesizers; consequently, datasets from these devices cannot be collected.

The tool proposed here addresses these challenges by providing fully automated and accurate dataset generation that is compatible with most hardware and software sound synthesizers, as well as other sound generators, such as electromechanically actuated acoustic and electroacoustic instruments. It offers an extensive set of functionalities to users through a comprehensive GUI. This tool complements our prior introduction focused on collecting datasets from audio effects [28]. The design and implementation, detailed in the following sections, are informed by our previous research in modeling musical devices using machine learning techniques, and in control strategies to manipulate the timbre of sound synthesizers. The tool, named Dataset Generator for Musical Devices (DGMD), is available as open-source software at <https://github.com/stefanofasciani/DGMD>.

2. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

2.1 Objectives and Choices

The proposed tool is designed to achieve key objectives in compatibility, automation, usability, and reproducibility, similar to the goals set for its companion audio effect version. It is compatible with any type of sound synthesizer or sound-generating device, including software plug-ins and hardware with interfaces like MIDI, CV/Gate, or manual controls. The tool aims to automate the dataset generation process as much as possible, reducing the need for manual intervention and enhancing efficiency. Furthermore, it is cross-platform and offers a comprehensive set of features and functionalities through a single GUI. It ensures the generation of consistent and reproducible datasets, providing reliable results across different iterations.

The sound synthesizer version of the DGMD described in this paper is implemented using Cycling '74 Max¹, as

¹ <https://cycling74.com/products/max>

the audio effects counterpart. This implementation environment offers an optimal trade-off between the objectives of compatibility and usability while providing the opportunity to develop a robust tool in terms of reproducibility and automation. Max natively interfaces with VST and AU software plugins and supports a variety of audio and MIDI drivers, allowing seamless interaction with hardware synthesizers through almost any sound card. Max allows for the creation of standalone, cross-platform applications with rich GUIs, effectively addressing potential issues related to operating system-specific system libraries, graphic libraries, and audio and MIDI drivers. Additionally, Max is a prudent choice for ensuring the tool’s longevity, as it has been continuously updated and maintained for over three decades. This track record suggests it can adapt to future changes in operating systems, ensuring the tool remains functional and relevant.

Although the dataset generation process is fully automated, significant time may still be required to compile the dataset. However, with software sound synthesizers, this time can be significantly reduced using Max’s non-realtime audio driver, which renders audio at the maximum rate allowed by the CPU’s computational power. While the speedup may not be as high as with VST hosts designed for text-based programming languages, there are other substantial benefits that support the choice of Max. In particular, when working in real-time mode, users can interact with the plug-in’s GUI to select variable parameters, understand their effect on the sound synthesis process, and fine-tune their ranges for inclusion in the dataset. This can be done while interactively listening to the sound synthesis output before generating the dataset.

While Max offers time-accurate objects for handling signals and messages used to interface with sound synthesizers, it has limitations when working with non-native data structures such as tables or implementing iterative algorithms. To address these limitations, the DGMD leverages Max’s native support for JavaScript through dedicated objects. This allows for the development of selected components of the tool in a text-based programming language, especially for those not aligning well with Max’s visual programming paradigm. Using JavaScript provides advantages like native cross-platform compatibility without the need to compile binaries. However, it’s important to note that Max’s JavaScript does not guarantee execution time or synchronization with the signal processing components. Therefore, all time-critical operations necessary for achieving dataset accuracy—such as interfacing with the sound synthesizer and handling audio signal processing and recording—are managed using Max’s native objects.

2.2 Interfacing Sound Synthesizers

The tool can receive audio input from sound synthesizers in either one (mono) or two (stereo) channels while sending various inputs to them. This includes messages to trigger note generation with arbitrary pitch, velocity, duration, up to 10 arbitrary synthesis parameters, pitch bending, which can be used for microtonality control, and aftertouch. The current implementation allows for easy ex-

tension beyond the limit of 10 parameters. The DGMD can drive the synthesizer using single notes or chords composed of up to 12 different notes, each with individual pitch and velocity. This limit is also easily extendable. Software synthesizer plugins are hosted directly within DGMD, with audio, MIDI, and parameters exchanged through the VST interface. Hardware synthesizers are interfaced using an external audio interface to receive generated audio. To send symbolic music information (i.e., notes) and synthesis parameters, DGMD supports both MIDI and CVs, as well as ad-hoc hybrid combinations of the two. However, when notes are triggered using V/Oct and Gate CVs, chord polyphony is not supported. While MIDI interfaces are widely available on most soundcards or as standalone devices, interfacing synthesizers with CVs requires specialized audio interfaces with DC-coupled I/Os and one audio channel per controlled parameter.

3. FUNCTIONALITY AND FEATURES

The GUI of the DGMD is shown in Figure 1, where orange overlay letters are used to label sections that serve different purposes. In the actual application, hovering the mouse over each GUI element displays its documentation.

3.1 Device Selection and Interface

Section ‘I’ of the GUI specifies the target sound synthesizer as either an internal software plugin or an external hardware unit. It allows selection of mono or stereo recording, adjusting the pre-recording gain, monitoring audio levels, and enabling listening through the monitoring audio output specified in section ‘G’. In section ‘G’, it’s possible to adjust the sampling rate, audio buffer size, and select the audio driver, including the ‘NonRealTime’ option to significantly speed up dataset generation with internal software plugins, and other advanced audio options.

When using internal plugins, section ‘L’ allows selection from default system folders or manual loading from a file. The plugin’s GUI can be shown in a separate window, and the ‘Monitor Plugin’ feature displays the name and value of parameters changed through the plugin’s GUI. This is essential because the VST interface’s parameter names and values used on the DGMD’s GUI often differ from those shown on the plugin’s GUI.

For external hardware sound synthesizers, the audio interface and selected channels for receiving audio are set in section ‘G’. If the synthesizer has MIDI-controllable parameters, the output port and channel are set and enabled in ‘H’, and the associated MIDI CC numbers for each parameter are configured in one of the ten ‘D’ sections. Additionally, CVs to control parameters can be enabled in ‘F’, utilizing a DC-coupled output audio interface specified in ‘G’, with individual parameter channels defined in ‘D’. Whether notes are triggered via MIDI or V/Oct and Gate CVs is set in section ‘H’. Channels for the V/Oct and Gate CVs note triggering are specified in the Pitch and Velocity sections ‘E’. Section ‘H’ allows specifying the maximum voltage level of the DC-coupled output interface, necessary for pitch control adjustment, and offers controls to

Figure 1. GUI of the Dataset Generator for Musical Devices (DGMD) tool, sound synthesizers version. The capital letters in the orange overlays indicate the different sections of the interface.

calibrate the generated V/Oct signal against the oscillator’s tuning. This tuning can be tracked with an external tuner or with the one provided in section ‘F’. Finally, the Gate CV can be set to a variable level to reflect the Velocity specified in section ‘E’.

Section ‘H’ allows specifying a MIDI input port and channel, enabling control of internal or external sound synthesizer parameters via MIDI CC (numbers specified in the ‘D’ sections), notes (Pitch and Velocity), Pitch Bend, and Aftertouch using an external MIDI controller or keyboard. This can also be accomplished with on-screen interactive elements associated with each parameter value, as well as with the on-screen keyboard. These features are advantageous for testing notes, parameter ranges for inclusion in the dataset, and setting parameters during manual dataset generation. MIDI input and the on-screen keyboard are restricted to monophony, as polyphony for generating chords is only managed internally as specified in section ‘F’.

3.2 Change Modes for Notes and Parameters

The GUI of the DGMD includes five nearly identical sections ‘E’ for specifying settings related to Pitch, Velocity, Duration, Pitch Bend, and Aftertouch. Additionally, there are ten identical sections ‘D’ that can be assigned to arbitrary synthesis parameters, controllable via the VST interface, MIDI CC messages, or CVs, as detailed previously. Pitch, Velocity, and Duration are always required to trigger the sound synthesizer and can be set to Fixed or Variable values across the dataset. The remaining parameters are varied and sent to the synthesizer during dataset generation only if set to ‘Enabled.’ For software plugins, synthesis parameters available on the VST interface can be selected by their names through a drop-down menu at the top of the ‘D’ sections. For external hardware synthesizers, within the same section, users can choose either the MIDI CC

number or the audio output channel for the CV, mapped to a unipolar or bipolar signal.

The current values for notes and synthesis parameters are displayed both numerically and as horizontal sliders in the bottom portion of each section ‘D’ and ‘E’. These indicators are interactive, enabling manual adjustments while tuning settings for dataset generation and visualizing changes during the process. Pitch, Velocity, and Aftertouch values use 7-bit integers, ranging from 0 to 127, with the first two displaying note names. In section ‘H’, the note name associated with the value 60 can be set as either $C3$ or $C4$. For Pitch Bend, it’s possible to select a 7-bit resolution ranging from 0 to 127 or a 14-bit resolution with values between -8192 and 8191 . Note durations are expressed in milliseconds. The ten synthesizer parameter values are represented in a normalized range from 0.0 to 1.0, as used by the VST interface. For all these synthesizer inputs, a specific range of interest—from a ‘Min’ to a ‘Max’ value—can be specified, within which they will vary during dataset generation.

In section ‘F’, chord settings can be defined so that each time a note is triggered, a chord is played instead of a single note. The note specified in the Pitch setting serves as the root of the chord, with up to 11 additional notes forming the chord, allowing for a maximum polyphony of 12. The pitch of the notes in the chord is expressed as a positive semitone offset from the root. The velocity of the notes in the chord can either follow the variable root’s velocity specified in ‘E’, or be individually set to fixed values.

The dataset can be generated according to four different ‘Parameter Change Mode’, specified in the section ‘A’: *Step*, *Random*, *Manual*, or *Sweep*.

In *Step* mode, the DGMD generates the dataset by sampling the values of ‘Enabled’ and ‘Variable’ parameters using a regular grid. Each parameter is sampled between the

‘Min’ to ‘Max’ values with an independent ‘Step’ value, specified by users in sections ‘D’ and ‘E’. Step values significantly impact the total number of parameter combinations, which is indicated in ‘A’ before dataset generation. When selecting the step values, it’s important to consider the actual resolution of the parameters being controlled, which may be influenced by the specific interfacing protocol, such as VST, MIDI, or CVs. Upon initiating dataset generation, the DGMD creates a generator object for parameter combinations, with each combination linked to a unique integer index. This index can be used to query the object for the current combination of synthesizer’s inputs. For each combination, input data, including note-related messages and synthesis parameters, is sent to the device, and the resulting audio signal is recorded. Audio is initially stored in memory buffers to ensure synchronization, and it is saved to disk only after recording is complete and time-sensitive operations have finished, before beginning the process for the next parameter combination. A separate audio file is created for each parameter combination’s recording. Given that the number of parameter combinations to include in the dataset may be large and the generation process lengthy, the DGMD allows users to specify the starting index for parameter combinations. This feature, along with the ability to save and recall all settings in user-defined presets in section ‘M’, and the system’s deterministic behavior, enables the creation of large datasets over multiple sessions without compromising consistency or accuracy.

In *Random* mode, the DGMD generates the dataset by drawing values from a series of independent uniform distributions, each corresponding to a different parameter. These distributions are confined to the selected range for each parameter, and the step value serves as a quantizer. The overall dataset generation process is similar to step mode, with random combinations drawn as needed, one at a time. However, due to the stochastic nature of this process, dataset generation is not absolutely reproducible, although datasets will be identical in size and statistically equivalent. The total number of random parameter combinations to be included in the dataset must be specified by users. Specifying the starting index facilitates the creation of large datasets over multiple sessions, though in this case, multiple files with tables of randomly drawn input combinations must be merged. When using the dataset to train machine learning models where parameters condition the model’s inference, high-density uniform grid sampling can cause overfitting. Random sampling is more effective in such cases. However, uniform sampling ensures better parameter space coverage for sparser grids. A dense uniform grid might still be preferable for analyzing, characterizing, or comparing the response of sound synthesizers.

The *Manual* mode allows users to select the synthesizer’s inputs and parameters individually. These are stored in a memory table when users manually trigger the process of sending the selected note and recording the synthesizer’s output. This mode serves various purposes, such as sampling the parameter space using different criteria, likely involving fewer combinations, or assisting in generating

datasets with external hardware sound synthesizers that require manual parameter adjustment. In such cases, users should replicate the settings from the synthesizer device within the DGMD interface before triggering the recording for each combination.

The *Sweep* mode differs significantly from other modes. In this mode, parameters are continuously varied while recording the dataset, each following a triangular wave with a defined range and frequency. In sections ‘D’ and ‘E’ of the GUI, users can set the ‘Sweep Rate,’ which is the frequency of the triangular oscillator controlling each parameter, spanning from the individual ‘Min’ to ‘Max’ values. Here, the concept of parameter combinations does not apply; instead, the desired dataset size is determined by the number of times notes are triggered and recorded, as specified in section ‘A’. For each note, the output signal is recorded into an audio file. Additionally, the sweeping parameters are recorded at audio rate into separate multi-channel audio files. The synchronized recording processes ensure that each track on both resulting files has identical durations, expressed in the number of samples. In this case as well, recordings are held in memory and only written to disk once the recording session is complete. Pitch, Velocity, and Duration, if set to ‘Variable’, are also varied by their individual triangular oscillator. However, continuous variation is not meaningful in their context. Instead, these values are sampled from the triangular wave at the moment the note is triggered, then stored in a memory table indexed by the repetition number, which also indexes the recorded audio files.

For hardware devices with a CV interface, synthesis parameters are transmitted as audio signals. However, for other interfaces like MIDI and VST, the triangular waves need to be sampled and their values sent to the synthesizer. In section ‘A’ of the GUI, users can set the ‘Sweep Update Rate,’ expressed in number of audio samples. This feature is only effective when the CV output is disabled and determines the clock rate driving a sample-and-hold block. This block downsamples the triangular waves, creating the actual set of values sent to the synthesizer, resulting in stepped triangular waves when control parameters are recorded. To accommodate the limited resolution of the interface controlling the parameters, users can select in section ‘A’ the bit depth for quantizing sweep values.

Sweep mode generates datasets for evaluating how sound synthesizers respond to continuous parameter variations. It can also be used to compare a synthesizer model’s behavior to the original device under gradual parameter changes. Datasets featuring dynamic synthesis parameters can enhance the training of machine learning models, potentially producing better outcomes than those using fixed parameter combinations, which necessitate interpolation for unseen values. The dataset’s value and the model’s learning potential depend on the chosen variation rates, with slower variations possibly benefiting training. To maximize parameter space coverage, parameter rates should not be integer multiples of each other. To ensure repeatability, the phases of triangular oscillators are reset to zero at the start of the dataset generation process.

Figure 2. Relationships between the DGMD timing settings and events involved in recording the synthesized sound for each parameter combination. This example captures only the sustained part of the synthesized sound and refers to using a synthesizer with a MIDI interface.

3.3 Time Settings and Synchronization

The DGMD allows users to set time values that govern the timing behavior of the dataset generation process. These settings are essential for synchronization and enable capturing specific temporal segments of the synthesizer’s signal. For each input parameter combination, the DGMD triggers note generation in the synthesizer. Notes can have ‘Fixed’ or ‘Variable’ duration t_d , as defined in ‘E’. For variable durations, the longest duration should guide timing adjustments. All time values are set in milliseconds in section ‘B’ and remain fixed throughout dataset generation. These include a delay t_u between sending a new set of parameters to the synthesizer and triggering the note. This delay allows synthesis parameters to take effect before note triggering and recording, accommodating device-specific latency. There is also a delay t_s between the note onset and the start of audio recording, and the audio recording duration t_r . The relationship between t_d , t_u , t_s , and t_r determines whether the dataset captures the entire note or possibly only the sustain phase, excluding the attack and/or release phase. Additionally, a delay t_e can be specified between the end of one recording and the start of the next. This ensures that the release phase does not interfere with subsequent recordings. The DGMD checks timing settings and alerts users if $t_s + t_r + t_e < t_d$, indicating that the note duration is excessive or the recording time is too short, which could compromise the integrity of the dataset. Figure 2 illustrates the relationships between the various timing settings and events involved in recording the synthesized sound for each parameter combination. It shows an example where the dataset records only the sustained part of the synthesized sound.

When notes are triggered via MIDI messages with external hardware synthesizers, a jitter of up to a few milliseconds can be observed in the synthesizers’ response. This jitter, arising from various factors, undermines the dataset’s accuracy and timing consistency. To address this, the DGMD offers a functionality that drives the synthesizer to generate a short pulse before the actual note. This pulse is another note with a short, definable duration and fixed pitch, velocity, and synthesis parameters. When this pulse is captured in the recorded audio files, it provides a consistent reference point that can be reliably identified using an onset detector. This allows all recordings to be trimmed

at a consistent point after the pulse, effectively minimizing or eliminating the MIDI jitter’s impact. However, achieving repeatable datasets with sample-level accuracy remains challenging with external sound synthesizers, as synchronizing the process with the phase of the synthesizers’ internal oscillators is often not feasible.

3.4 File Input and Outputs

The DGMD produces several output files. In section ‘C’ of the GUI, it is possible to specify the directory for saving output files and a prefix for all generated files. In *Step*, *Random*, and *Manual* modes, the tool creates a separate uncompressed mono or stereo wave audio file for each parameter combination in the dataset. Audio filenames include an integer index that corresponds to the parameter combination detailed in the generated CSV file, which also includes VST parameter names for internal plugins. The CSV file is exported automatically after dataset generation, but users have the option to export it manually if the process is interrupted. The step mode parameter combination generator is initialized with the ‘Update’ button in section ‘A’. Both the generator and the memory table for random and manual modes can be cleared using the ‘Reset’ button. Additionally, in section ‘C’, users have the option to include associated parameter values in the audio file names.

In *Sweep* mode, two uncompressed wave audio files are generated for each input stimulus repetition. The first file records the synthesizer’s output, while the second is a multichannel file containing audio-rate recordings of the sweeping parameters, post downsampling and decimation as explained in Section 3.2. These wave files use the system sampling rate set in section ‘D’ of the GUI. The synthesizer output is saved in a 32-bit floating point format, whereas parameters are recorded in a 24-bit integer format. Both files include the same integer index to link to data in the CSV file, which contains information on Pitch, Velocity, and Duration for triggering notes, set as ‘Fixed’, or sampled from the respective triangular waves when set as ‘Variable’. Recording sweeping parameter as audio signals ensures optimal alignment of input and output data, simplifying dataset use, especially for machine learning that requires matching input-output pairs.

The described modalities allow for the creation of simple pitch patterns that can be extended to chords with a fixed configuration throughout the dataset, as specified in ‘F’. To overcome this limitation, the DGMD can automatically generate collections of datasets with consistent overall settings but bypassing the GUI’s Pitch, Velocity, and Chord settings, drawing this information from a user-provided file. Users can provide an ‘Extend’ CSV file via section ‘A’, containing as many rows as needed for each dataset repetition. Each row consists of a unique string to extend the prefix specified in ‘C’ for filenames, followed by up to 24 integer values ranging from 0 to 127. These values define up to 12 pitch and velocity pairs, creating different polyphonic patterns as input to the sound synthesizer for each repetition of the dataset generation process. In this setup, the generated CSV files include information only for the remaining parameters, excluding Pitch and Velocity.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduced the Dataset Generator for Musical Devices (DGMD), specifically the version designed for sound synthesizers. It is a standalone software designed to generate accurate and reproducible datasets from any software or hardware sound synthesizer. DGMD offers a comprehensive set of features and functionalities inspired by various research directions focused on sound synthesizers, with a primary emphasis on machine learning applications. Both DGMD and its video tutorial are freely available at <https://github.com/stefanofasciani/DGMD>.

5. REFERENCES

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